

AUTOMATED MULTIPLE PLANT WATERING SYSTEM

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Abstract

In this paper, we proposed an automated system of plant watering system using Arduino. Most of the existing systems of automated plant watering are suitable for only one plant and multiple plants sprinklers are used or multiple pipes are generally used. The proposed model is different from the existing ones because the system is designed for efficiently watering multiple plants. The plants are arranged in an array and only one water pipe is used which is moved to the desired location using a trolley system. The desired plant pot is selected from the readings of the moisture sensor and control of the whole is done using Arduino. The proposed model used the water more efficiently and judiciously and it has high flexibility that any number of plant pots can be added in a hassle-free manner.

Keywords:

Automated watering system, multiple plants, Arduino, moisture sensor.

1. INTRODUCTION

Water is a necessity for survival in almost all living things. Plants need water for their growth and they get it from the soil. Soil not only provides water but other components like minerals also. Whenever a plant requires water it will be absorbed from the water present in the soil, therefore the soil needs to be hydrated. In a garden, the water in the soil is provided from external sources like rain on a rainy day or by a gardener. Usually, the gardener provides water to the plants two times a day, one in the morning and one in the evening. The disadvantages of providing water manually by gardener or user are:

- The user does not know when the plant requires water.
- The user does not know how much water is required by a plant.

A constant monitor of the plant is required by the gardener and he/she fails to provide water then the plants may not survive. The problem will be more if a family leaves for vacation and the plants are left without water. Also due to scarcity of water in cities, the water resources should be dealt with properly in a garden which demands a lot of water. The necessity for an alternative arrangement for providing solutions is required. If plant watering is automated, then some of the problems mentioned above may be alleviated. Therefore an automated plant watering system is more desirable which can provide big relief to gardeners.

This present work deals with the development of solutions for automated plant watering systems. The system is based on a moisture sensor and the whole system is controlled by Arduino. The model is designed for multiple plant watering automatically. The details of the proposed model are explained in the subsequent sections.

Some earlier research work in this direction can be found in the work proposed by the authors in [1] and [2]. Their works were

mainly focused on the monitoring of water content of the soil and information is sent to the user. The information provided is crop temperature and water status in [1] and a real-time soil water monitoring system is proposed in [2]. The design of an Arduino-based plant watering system is presented by the author in [3]. The model is a simple demonstration of a single plant watering system based on Arduino using the soil water content information obtained from a moisture sensor. The works proposed in [4] and [5] are also models for plant watering systems. Both the models are the same except for the use of mobile applications for sending a report, in the model proposed by the authors in [5]. The overall activity is reported to the user through a mobile application. Some other research works and methods for automatic irrigation systems can be found in the literatures [6]-[9] and the authors in [10] proposed an Internet of Things (IoT) based model that incorporates the weather information in the design.

The remainder of the paper is organized as follows. A statement of the problem is given in section 2. A detail of the proposed model is given in section 3 and section 4 finally concludes the paper.

2. PROBLEM STATEMENT

The problem deals with the design of an automated watering system for multiple plants. The plants under consideration are assumed as potted plants. We aim to propose a model in which the plants are arranged in such a fashion that maximum plants can be covered with minimum resources. The design should be such that it is flexible for adding newly potted plants. Finally, the design should be suitable for other similar purposes.

3. PROPOSED SYSTEM

In this section, we present the model of the proposed automatic multiple plant watering system and its working. A graphic model of the proposed system is shown in Fig.1. The plants in the flower pot are arranged in an array using a flower stand. A water pipe is used which is moved to the desired pot location using a motor in a trolley system. The desired plant pot is selected from the readings of the moisture sensor and control of the whole system is done using Arduino.

A working model of the proposed system is as shown in Fig.2. The plants under consideration are assumed as potted plants. We have designed the system for automatic watering of three plants arranged in an array.

Fig. 1. Proposed model of automatic plant watering system.

Fig. 2. Setup of the proposed system.

3.1 Circuit Components Used in the Model

The components required for the design of the proposed system are as follows:

- *Arduino Uno*: We have used the Arduino Uno kit which is based on the ATmega328P-8 bit AVR family microcontroller and for programming is done through ArduinoIDE (1.0.6 Version).
- *Moisture sensor*: A simple moisture sensor is used that works with 5 V DC. Depending upon the moisture content it generates a corresponding analog output.
- *Submersible pump*: For the present work we have used a submersible water pump which is a mini-size water pump that works with 12V DC. Submersibles are more efficient than jet pumps which are extremely simple and easy to use.

- *Power supply*: We used an SMPS power supply of rating +5V, 2A and +12V,1A. The mechanized water sprayer is operated with a +5V supply and +12V to run the submersible water pump. A rechargeable battery backup is also provided for running the system in case of power failure.

3.2 Working on the proposed system

The working of the model is explained below. The heart of the system is the controller which is designed using Arduino. The controller takes moisture content data from the sensors placed on the soil of the three flower pots. According to the reading of the different sensors, the following operation will be performed:-

- Every program cycle checks the reading on the analog read pin (A0, A1, A2) of the Arduino kit and the reading is converted to a percentage and is displayed on the display unit.
- For the present work, maximum plant moisture content has been assigned as 40%. If the reading from any of the moisture sensors is less than 40% then the following action follows:
- The mechanized water sprayer moves forward till it reaches the position of flower pot whose moisture content is less than 40%. As it reaches the flower pot position, a water pump is initiated and the shower is started. The shower continues till the moisture content exceeds 40%. As the moisture content exceeds 40% showering is stop and the mechanized water sprayer moves to the initial position.

The summary of the implementation of the proposed model is depicted in the flowchart as shown in Fig.3. The flowchart shown in Fig.3 is the process flow when the moisture content of flower pot 'A' is less than 40 %. The same procedure will be followed for the remaining flower pots.

4 CONCLUSION

In this paper, we have proposed a model for automatic multiple plant watering. The model is based on the soil moisture content of the plants with controlling done by Arduino. For experimental purposes, we have designed a prototype model for three flower pot plants and it performed satisfactorily. The proposed model is robust in that it can be extended for any number of plants in a hassle-free manner. The model provides a system where water is used judiciously and with less user intervention.

Fig. 3. Flowchart of flow process of the proposed system.

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